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DECONSTRUCTING THE POST-GRADUATE PROJECT: TIME FOR CHANGE?

Lauren Schrock

Study Skills Lead,
Study, Professional & Analytical Skills Team
WMG
University of Warwick

Robin Clark

Executive Head of Education
WMG
University of Warwick

Maryam Masood

Analytical Skills Lead,
Study, Professional & Analytical Skills Team
WMG
University of Warwick

Jane Andrews

Study, Professional & Analytical Skills Team Lead
WMG
University of Warwick

Graeme Knowles

Head of Education Innovation Group
WMG
University of Warwick

ABSTRACT

Focusing on what is an almost universal facet of graduate level education, the 'Research Dissertation', this paper examines how students are prepared to conduct an independent piece of research in three areas of study associated with engineering or industrial management. Focusing on the provision of 'Study Skills and 'Research Methods' training, 62 UK universities were identified as offering courses in one or more of the following programme areas: MSc Engineering Management: MSc Supply Chain and / or Logistics Management: MSc Project and / or Operational Management. An analytical framework was developed and data collected.

This paper presents the data before discussing how one large engineering education department in the UK has completely reviewed and revamped how students are prepared for their dissertation. Attention is given to the pedagogic approach and academic content whilst the paper brings the issues up to date by briefly touching on how the students are being supported during the Covid19 Pandemic.

Keywords: Dissertation, Student Project, Study Skills, Graduate study

1. Introduction: Background on the Case Study Organisation

This paper discusses the preparatory work undertaken in renewing the way in which a large cohort of graduate students within one of the UK's largest engineering education faculties are supported in making the transition to a higher level of study and prepared for the 'cornerstone' of their postgraduate education: the MSc dissertation. Situated in a large Russell Group University, the faculty houses just under 1,500 postgraduate students studying a range of engineering and engineering related programmes. The majority of students are full-time and follow courses of study which lead to qualifications in Engineering Management, Supply Chain and / or Logistics Management: Project and / or Operations Management. All students are required to conduct an independent piece of research in the form of a MSc Dissertation; this is currently allocated 90 credits or half of the credits for their degree. The one module which is compulsory to all, yet currently not part of any credited programme, is Study, Professional & Analytical Skills (SPA). Tasked with making SPA 'credit bearing' as part of a Departmental Academic Review of 16 postgraduate programmes, the SPA teaching team are in the process of improving the academic quality of the module content whilst enhancing individual student support. As part of the changes, the credit value of the Dissertation will change from 90 to 60 credits.

This paper looks at one of the processes involved in planning the future SPA Module: a benchmarking exercise in which a comparative analysis of the three subject areas (Engineering Management: Supply Chain / Logistics Management: Project /

Operational Management) was undertaken across the UK Higher Education Sector. The paper concludes by identifying how the benchmarking exercise is being used to inform the development of the new module and by commenting on the response to the current 'Covid19' Pandemic while situation, questioning to what degree the current situation will impact future provision.

2. Why Prepare Students for their Dissertation? A question of 'transferable skills'.

Throughout the first two decades of the 21st Century numerous academic studies have focused on *what* skills and competencies future engineers need to learn in terms of technical content^[1,2] whilst other have highlighted the need for engineering students to be equipped with 'softer' transferable skills including academic writing, verbal presentation and critical thinking skills^[3,4,5]. However, in 2020, as the Covid19 Pandemic spreads across the world, the need to expand the public mind-set about what engineering is and what engineers *do* has possibly never been more important^[6,7]. Indeed, the global expectation that engineering companies respond to the current crisis by providing fast, viable solutions to a global demand for medical equipment, such as ventilators and protective clothing, is unprecedented^[8]. Likewise, the need for highly skilled logisticians, able to envision and enact the supply chain at a time when demand is unparalleled, has brought an academic discipline that usually sits on the edge of what is considered 'engineering education' to the public forefront^[9].

It is within this contemporary global context that this very local paper is set. Drawing attention to the practical and pedagogic problems of equipping a cohort of over 1,200 students with the necessary skills to conduct an independent piece of research. This was challenging before Covid19, at this moment in time sometimes feels overwhelming. Grounded in a model of engineering education proposed by two of the paper authors^[10] and set within a prestigious Russell Group University, the discussion in this paper highlights the challenges of designing and implementing suitable provision for a multinational cohort of students.

2.2 The Context: Employability & Pedagogical Frailty

In considering the role played by higher education in equipping graduates with transferable employability skills, one key factor determining what students within the European Union are taught is the Bologna Declaration [1999] and the EHEA^[12]. Since Bologna, numerous EU treaties and agreements^[13,14] have shaped how engineering and other university courses are designed with the concept of employability being shared across programmes, disciplines and countries alike. Likewise, a number of academic studies have considered what skills new graduates are expected to possess upon becoming employed^[15,16]. Additionally, a considerable body of literature looks specifically at the employability skills and competencies that engineering graduates need to possess upon graduation^[17,18,19].

In considering the task of preparing engineering and engineering-related students for success at postgraduate level, the teaching team adopted an approach developed by two of the paper authors, that of Synergetic Configuration within the auspices of the RVS Model of Engineering Education^[10,20]. To assure academic rigour and validity, the RVS Model was considered from the epistemological stance proposed within the concept of pedagogical frailty^[21,22]. It is important to note that culturally, immediately prior to the project taking place, the faculty had undergone a period of organisational change, something which had unsettled some colleagues^[23, 24]. For the module concerned such change was necessary as, up until this point in time, learning has been scaffolded onto a teacher-centred pedagogy whereby facts and theories were transmitted by rote and deep learning did not occur^[25,26].

2.3 WMG: Reviewing & Renewing Study & Methodological Skills Training

WMG represents one of the largest postgraduate engineering education faculties within the UK. In 2019 / 2020 there were over 1,500 mostly full-time students enrolled on a range of engineering and engineering management related programmes. The Study, Professional & Analytical Skills (SPA) Module is taught to over 1,200 full-time, residential students, the majority of whom originate from China and surrounding countries. A critical review of the module occurred in the summer of 2019 and revealed four areas whereby the module content needed to be enhanced for rigour and validity:

1. Poor student engagement in study skills sessions
2. Sporadic engagement in research methods lectures
3. An overloading of information on the VLE
4. A lack of constructive alignment^[27] with wider programmes and inadequately aligned learning outcomes.

3. Comparative Analysis of Cross-Institutional Provision: The Approach

The purpose of conducting a benchmarking study of study skills and research methods training at MSc level within the UK was to enable the teaching team to gain an understanding of how comparable programmes support and prepare students to conduct an independent piece of research.

3.1 Methodology

An analytical framework was developed and the following variables recorded: Name and type of HEI offering one of the three courses (all data has been anonymised prior to publication),: Provision of pre-dissertation study skills and methodology training: Number of credits allocated to pre-dissertation study skills and methodology training: Faculty in which the courses were offered (Engineering / Applied Science, or Business / Social Science). Within the sample of 62 HEIs, 90 separate courses were identified in total. Of these, 70 offered research methods and study skills training to students as part of the formal learning programme.

4. Cross-Institutional Provision of Support for MSc Project: Findings

The first variable examined related to the amount of credits associated with the MSc Dissertation. Looking at the three subjects separately, the data in Table 1, below, reveals that the vast majority of projects were given a credit value of 60 [$N=54$]. The lowest number of credits allocated to the dissertation was 30. One institution offering an MSc in the subject of Supply Chain / Logistics Management did not have a Dissertation.

Table 1: Credit value allocated to MSc Dissertation by Subject area.

Credit Value for Dissertation	Engineering Management	Supply Chain / Logistics Management	Project / Operations Management	n
60	20	20	14	54
45	2	3	2	7
40	1			1
30	1	1		2
Not shown	8	13	7	28
No Project		1		1
Total	32	38	23	93

Having looked at the credit value of the programmes, the next task was to identify in which faculty the three programmes were offered. Table 2, below reveals that the vast majority of Engineering Management courses are offered in Engineering Faculties. Conversely, the opposite is true of Supply Chain / Logistics courses where most are provided in a Business School setting. Project / Operational Management course were almost equally spread between the two.

The data shown below in Table 3 shows that the provision of research methods per faculty. It reveals that 74% of courses in Engineering Faculties and 78% in Business or Social Science

faculties provided a credited study skills and / or research methods training for students. Table 4, below, shows the majority of the study skills and / or research methods modules had a value of 15 credits (7.5 CATS).

Table 3: Total courses offered by faculty & provision of credited study skills and research methods training

Faculty	N [% of total]	Accredited Study Skills / Research Methods training: N [% of courses offered]
Engineering / Applied Science	53 [57%]	39 [74%]
Business / Social Science	40 [43%]	31 [78%]
Total	93	70

Table 4: Credit value of study skills / research methods training across the sample

Credit Value	N
30	2
20	15
15	25
12	2
10	3
Credit rating not noted	25
No module offered	21
Total	93

5. Discussion: Building a 'Credit Bearing' Module to Support the Dissertation and Wider Studies

Having established the uniqueness of all three subject areas within a Faculty of Engineering (only one other Engineering Faculty offered all three courses), the work required to make SPA a '15 credit' module began. With the first Intended Learning Outcome focusing on Independent Learning Skills, the need to develop a signature pedagogy which serves the needs of 16 different courses and a largely international cohort is of paramount importance^[28,29]. As such a diverse range of subjects are offered with the first few weeks, covering a range of topics including: 'An introduction to Academic Writing'; 'Using the Library'; 'Note Taking'; 'Avoiding Plagiarism'; 'Critical Thinking'; 'Joining a Professional Body'; and 'Studying in the UK'. Following the student learning journey, 'Ethics in Research and Applying for Ethical Approval' is introduced at the beginning of term 2, whilst high level 'Analytical and Study Skills' sessions are delivered throughout terms 2 and 3. Learning provision continues beyond term 3 into the summer whereupon attention turns to 'Writing at a Graduate Level' and 'Constructing a Dissertation'.

As the necessary planning and quality control process for the credit bearing module were just about to be enacted, the Covid19 Pandemic hit the UK, resulting in face-to-face teaching being replaced by a 100% on-line approach. This put additional pressures on the team as the need to prioritise current offerings over future options took precedence. However, on the plus side, the enforced period of intense working has enabled a pedagogically and strategically module to be developed. One that is academically aligned to the wider programmes and modules and in which a more academic emphasis on Professional Skills is being introduced alongside Study and Analytical Skills. From October-December 2020 SPA: Study, Professional & Analytical Skills, will support students throughout their postgraduate learning journey by offering a combination of synchronous and asynchronous learning experiences. This has been achieved by:

- i. Developing and designing the curriculum based upon the concept of **Synergetic Configuration** introduced within the **RVS Model of Engineering Education** developed by Clark & Andrews (2014)^[10].
- ii. **Purposefully developing and designing learning materials** to fit into one of the three main strands:
 - **Study Skills:** Study skills is divided into three distinctive phases. The first one, aimed at engendering a sense of belonging within individual students^[29,30,31], is aligned with 'Welcome Week' and included a formative piece of written work. A 'marking and feedback' rubric is being developed to enable to teaching team to mark and provide feedback within the first few weeks of term.
 - **Professional Skills:** This new stream has been purposefully designed so as to make sure that the module is academically **and** vocationally

relevant. Bearing in mind the need to create a module which will form part of a number of programmes that are accredited by different professional bodies, employability and the need to equip and measure students' transferable skills is central.

- **Analytical Skills:** The final stream relates both to critical analytical skills and research methodology. A significant change to the previous provision is the introduction of workshops on how to use 'online' analytical and other research tools. Whilst the majority of this stream focuses on management research, aimed at equipping future engineering managers with the ability to conduct a piece of industrially valid management research, topics such as advanced statistics, experimental approaches and other technological / engineering research methodologies are offered alongside 'expert workshops'.
- iii. **Redevelopment of Learning Materials:** The learning materials are being re-written so as to better reflect the wider requirements of all of the MSc programmes. All learning materials will be provided in a range of different formats including: Small group workshops: Large group teaching sessions held at weekends: Specialist tutorials: Pre-recordings of key content: Workbooks: On-line provision including interactive quizzes and short films.
- iv. **Redesign of the VLE:** The VLE is constantly being refreshed and renewed and will again be completely redesigned for the beginning of the new academic year.
- v. **Improved Student Communication & Support:** Weekly updates and emails are sent to the students to remind them of what is occurring in the following week and also to send useful hints and tips about learning. Additional 'wellbeing' support and academic tutorials are offered.

6. Concluding Remarks: Moving forward at a time of uncertainty

This paper relates to an ongoing project in which the teaching of Study, Professional and Analytical Skills is being reviewed and renewed with the intention of making sure that students are academically supported in such a way that provides them with the necessary high-level skills needed to succeed. Developing, designing and introducing a credit bearing module to meet the needs of an academically and ethnically diverse group of students, studying on 16 different courses has proved challenging. The fact that up until this point in time the module was not incorporated as an academic component of the wider programmes which meant there was a lack of ownership and leadership. Conversely, when redesigning the module, problems arose in which colleagues insisted their course requirements be prioritised over others. The SPA module has a full-time teaching staff of 2 with a module lead allocated 0.2 of their role dedicated to managing the module. Given the number of students, which is expected to be similar in the academic year beginning in 2020 despite Covid19, the staff-student ratio is exceptionally low. This has proved a challenge throughout the module design process.

The Covid19 Pandemic has seen the whole of the current module content move on-line in a matter of days. Having pre-recorded key content, the teaching team were at an advantage in comparison to other colleagues. Hence in the period when formal teaching was temporarily suspended to allow materials to be streamed via Microsoft Teams, full use was made of the Study Skills and Research Methodology tools and materials. Furthermore, for a short period of time the SPA team were the main academic team supporting students as lectures were suspended due to lockdown with students returning to their home countries. Providing a high level of academic support over this period of uncertainty enabled students to continue to work on their dissertations whilst awaiting the recommencement of teaching.

In conclusion, the benchmarking exercise discussed in this paper revealed that WMG is the only UK university currently offering a 90 credit Dissertation for the three subjects examined. It is also one of only a handful of HEIs that does not currently offer a credit bearing *study skills and research methods* focused module. That both of these are being changed in the future can only be good news for the student experience and whilst Covid19 has slightly changed the 'goal-posts', the teaching team remain dedicated to developing a highly transferable and excellent quality resource.

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